

Causal inference and sensitivity analysis for binary outcome models

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Introduction

In recent years, methods have been developed to decompose the causal effect of a covariate (X) on an outcome random variable (Y) into the direct effect and a number of indirect effects, each of them attributable to different mediators along the pathways from X to Y . A mediator is a random variable that is a response of X and, in turn, influences Y . The investigation helps in making informed decisions in several fields, ranging from medicine to public interventions. These methods are known as "mediation analysis". The assumptions needed to identify causal effects are rather complex (Pearl, 2014).

Methods

With reference to a binary response Y , we aim at developing sensitivity analysis against the identifying assumptions. This strand of literature is not new, see e.g. Imai and Yamamoto (2013) or VanderWeele (2015, Ch. 3), and requires the investigation of the marginal model of X on Y as induced by the system. Results of Stanghellini and Doretti (2019) and Raggi et al. (2021) can be opportunely modified to account for a binary unobserved confounder. Other parametric and nonparametric structure may also be investigated. Ordered response may also be considered, as in Stanghellini and Kateri (2022).

Results

The formulation would allow to lay down parametrically the necessary conditions to identify causal effects and therefore to determine the set of parameters that can be modified to perform sensitivity analysis. If parameters are naturally bounded, this can also lead to uncertainty intervals.

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